

COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF PHARMACEUTICS: EXPERIENCE AND PROSPECTS

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Relevance: international cooperation in pharmaceuticals is manifested through the registration of foreign medicines, which contributes to expanding public access to innovative therapies and improving quality standards. Moreover, globalization and the increasing prevalence of chronic diseases require joint efforts of different countries to accelerate the development and distribution of effective medicines.

Purpose of the study: the aim of the study is to analyze the dynamics of foreign medicines registration by pharmacotherapeutic groups in Uzbekistan over the past five years, to identify leading countries in international cooperation, and to determine the most clinically relevant medicines.

Materials and methods: the research was based on official registry data (2020–2025) provided by the Center for Pharmaceutical Safety of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The analysis included information on the number of registered foreign medicines, distributed by manufacturing countries and pharmacotherapeutic groups. A comparative analysis method was applied, and the obtained results were presented as percentages.

Results: The development of international cooperation in the pharmaceutical sector of Uzbekistan is associated with the expansion of partnerships with leading global manufacturers, the active introduction of innovative and biotechnological medicines, as well as the establishment of joint research projects. Between 2020 and 2025, more than 6,000 medicines were registered in Uzbekistan, over 3,000 of which were foreign. The leading positions in terms of registered medicines are occupied by India (40%), Russia (10%), Turkey and Ukraine (8% each), which indicates a high degree of integration of the national pharmaceutical market into the global system. Among the registered medicines, the largest share belongs to antibiotics, antineoplastic agents, and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Overall, there is a tendency toward an increase in the share of innovative foreign medicines, which contributes to the development of the pharmaceutical sector in the country and strengthens the national healthcare system.

Conclusions: over the past five years, Uzbekistan has demonstrated a steady increase in the number of registered foreign medicines. The majority of registrations come from India, Russia, Turkey, and Ukraine, which confirms the intensification of international pharmaceutical cooperation and the integration of the national market into the global system. The dominance of antibiotics, antineoplastic agents, and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs among registered medicines reflects the current needs of healthcare. At the same time, the growing share of innovative foreign medicines contributes to improving the quality of pharmaceutical care and strengthening the country's drug safety.